
A Study on Impact of Social Media Content Management on Consumer Behaviour and Purchase Preferences

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ABSTRACT

Media technologies have greatly influenced human behaviour and created a link between the virtual and real worlds. Globally, content engagement has significantly impacted customer behaviour and purchasing decisions. The media can inspire you to take action, give you ideas, and motivate you to start what you see in today's digital world. People's behaviour, lifestyle, morals, and outcomes can all be influenced by the media can have both beneficial and negative impacts, as it creates a new world rather than reflecting reality. The influence of media on consumer behaviour and preferences has been substantial. Marketers are progressively using social media as a key mechanism for reaching their target audience. Influencer marketing is a common strategy for companies to promote their products through media influencers. Media has changed our social interactions and purchasing habits. This study's primary goal is to investigate how media affects consumer preferences and behaviour. This study aims to determine the impact of trending mass media on consumer behaviour, determining if individuals respond similarly to the virtual world or focus on the practical side. With a sample size of 150 individuals in Hyderabad, a questionnaire-based survey was conducted which included questions on the subject's behaviour, influence, preferences, and thoughts. The results revealed that the purchasing decision was influenced by reviews

in majority of the cases and furthermore, entertaining content grabbed the attention of the viewers.

1. Introduction

Influencers are now key players in the digital world, impacting not just consumer choices but also societal conventions and the development of online cultures. They are no longer only trendsetters or promotional tools. Due to their extensive reach and capacity to foster trust, they are essential in both business endeavours and social discussions that have an impact on both cultural ideals and brand recognition. The study highlights the need for a more thorough examination of influencers' function in reflecting and occasionally opposing societal trends, given their increasing significance in forming public discourse and digital identities.

The relationship between influencers and their followers is shifting along with the digital landscape, becoming more sincere and value-driven. This change highlights how crucial digital literacy is to comprehending and managing the influencer market. The study emphasizes the substantial, diverse influence of social media influencers, identifying them as important catalysts for change. In order to maximize their beneficial effects while negotiating ethical issues, their influence comes with both opportunities and problems that must be carefully considered. The rapidly evolving role of influencers in digital culture will surely necessitate ongoing consideration and re-evaluation as time passes by.

2. Literature Review

To comprehend the complex dynamics of social media influencers' effects on consumer attitudes, a theoretical framework has been developed. According to **Christy M. Cook, Lubna Nafees and James E. Stoddard (2020)**, there is a favourable correlation between the credibility of influencer sources and their knowledge, compassion, and reliability.

Users' social media involvement, perception of knowledge acquisition, and social self-efficacy all increase after following a SMI. According to **Ben Wasik (2023)**, these impacts have a beneficial effect on social relationships both offline and online. This realization is essential, particularly in light of anxieties about false information on social media and the pervasive use of SMI content that frequently lacks verification for veracity and accuracy.

Social media content has a direct impact on user engagement behaviour, with influencers exhibiting both passive and active engagement based on format and platform. As stated by, **Rebecca Dolan, Hamidreza**

Shahbaznezhad and Mona Rashidirad (2021), the context of social media material influences its effectiveness in engaging users. These findings help to improve our knowledge of user engagement and experiences on social media platforms by furnishing concrete intuition into the interactions of content types and situations.

Exploring the relationship between fan tastes, para-social engagement, and spoken words in the age of influencer marketing is the key to social media influencing. **Cheng-Yong Liu ,Yu-Hsi Yuan, Yi-Cheng Yeh and Chia-Huei Wu (2022)** observed that With influencers having a variety of roles in business, politics, and charity, the internet and social media have become essential tools for self-promotion and online branding. The study illustrates how effective influencer marketing on social media could promote economic growth and competitiveness in today's changing marketplace.

McKinsey & Company's India studies show that digital influencers can have tremendous impact. According to their findings, 80% of consumers will consider a new company after receiving a reference from a significant influencer. Every day, crores of items are advertised, each supported by an equal number of influencers. They work tirelessly to develop relationships with their followers, keeping many levels of involvement in mind: trust-building, awareness of their specialized category, and advertising. According to **McKinsey's** research, Gen Z values online communities for their ability to unite and mobilize individuals from diverse economic backgrounds around common causes. This might be looked at as even if Gen Z is varied in terms of ethnicity, gender, and purchasing.

Lee, J , Han, S. H. and Masuda, H. (2022) suggested that influencer marketing on social media is huge right now and is getting all the attention. When the public or followers perceive the influencer as dependable, they make larger purchases. Perceived competence and trustworthiness are terms associated with influencers, or more precisely, influencer credibility. In addition, consumers might establish pseudo-social connections with celebrities through influencer marketing. There is a significant impact from the influencer's behaviour and attitude. Customers are more likely to make purchases when they believe an influencer is trustworthy, therefore earning their trust is crucial.

Shwetha N S, Vinutha H K (2024) When it comes to choosing a channel for marketing strategy for any firm, influencer marketing has grown significantly. In addition to providing customers with incentives in the form of discounts and offers, it has assisted consumers in becoming aware of a wide range of brands, goods, and possibilities for purchases. Working with influencers can be difficult, but if done well, the rewards on investment are unparalleled. Because of marketers' rising yields, customers should expect to see a considerable increase in influencer marketing in their feeds in the near future. Unquestionably,

influencer marketing has changed how companies communicate with customers by providing special advantages in terms of engagement and authenticity.

Prof. Dr. Suryakant Ratan Chaugule (2024) Businesses can utilize influencer marketing as a potent tool to interact with their audiences in a genuine way. It has been demonstrated to boost sales, connect with a particular audience, build trust, encourage devoted followers, keep clients, and leave a lasting impression. Additionally, the cost-effectiveness and ability to target particular demographics demonstrate the versatility and effectiveness of influencer marketing strategies. As businesses adapt to the digital age, influencer marketing continues to be a crucial part of successful marketing initiatives. It fosters genuine relationships and promotes brand advocacy among diverse audiences.

According to **M Nick Hajli (2014)**, The component that has a strong impact on purchase intention is perceived usefulness. Participants are more inclined to make purchases using social networking sites when they receive high-quality information or systems. According to data study, the intention to purchase through social networking sites is more influenced by perceived utility than by trust. As a result, customers rely on social media platforms as being more useful when they are of higher quality.

Haenlein and Kaplan (2010) talk about how peer pressure, self-expression, and social identity impact consumer behavior on social media. Particularly in the fashion and lifestyle industries, consumers may indulge in lavish spending in an attempt to win favor or likes.

3. Objectives of the study:

- To analyze the significance of influencers on participants purchasing decisions and trust levels in influencer recommendations.
- To study the level of engagement with influencer content by analyzing participants interactions such as likes, comments, and shares.
- To analyze the extent to which influencers shape participants lifestyle choices and opinions on social issues.
- To Investigate how following influencers affects participants online and offline social interactions.
- To study the insights into participants expectations regarding the future influence and evolving role of social media influencers in society.

➤ To understand the extent of awareness regarding influencers.

Aligning with the above objectives, a questionnaire has been drafted. Data was collected using random sampling technique from 150 respondents and the analysis was carried out.

3.1 Methodology

Quantitative survey approach was performed. Data from 150 consumers was collected through Google forms and personal interviews. The sample comprised of a wide range of age groups and geographic sites. SPSS version 26 was employed for analysis which includes frequency distribution and factor analysis to identify relationships among variables.

4. Data Analysis

4.1 ANALYSIS - I

Table 1- Frequency Table

S.No	Parameter	Response	Frequency
1	Age	Below 19	36
		20-39	76
		40-59	28
		60 and above	10
2	Gender	Male	60
		Female	90
3	Location	Urban	90
		Suburban	28
		Rural	32
4	Amount of the time spent on social media per day	< an hour	28
		1-5 hours	102
		5-10 hours	20

5	Effect of influencer's recommendations on purchase	yes	82
		unsure	68
6	Level of satisfaction with the purchase	Very satisfied	26
		Satisfied	47
		Not Satisfied	27
5. 7	6. Extent of influence of likes, shares and comments on your shopping choices	Very much	18
		Mostly	28
		Neutral	36
		A little	27
		Doesn't much	41
8	Discuss influencer related content with friends or family	Never	33
		Rarely	45
		Occasionally	51
		Frequently	19
		Consistently	2
9	Attended events or meet-ups organized by influencers	Regularly	13
		Once a month	13
		Less than a month	24
		Never	100
10	Frequency of engagement with influencer content	Always	13
		Most of the time	28

		Sometimes	63
		Never	46
7. 11	8. Influencers impact on communication between consumers and businesses	Trust Building	38
		Purchase Influence	63
		Real-time feedback	49
12	Social media influencers impact on overall behavior and preferences of users	Positive Impact	47
		Negative Impact	16
		Diverse Preferences	53
		Brand Loyalty	18
		Impulse Buying	16
13	Social media influencers impact on social interactions among users	Strength and connections	27
		Influence trends	72
		Create divisions	19
		No impact	32
14	Future role of social media influencers in society	Supporting causes	16
		Being authentic	14
		Sharing knowledge	63
		Global trendsetters	16
		Innovative earnings	41

Interpretation:

From the above table, the following observations were made :-

- Majority i.e.,51%(76) of the respondents are between 20-39 years showing a strong representation of adults, 24%(36) are below 19years of age and only 6% (10) are aged above 60 years indicating limited participation from older demographics.
- Female respondents dominate (60%) the study indicating more interest towards influencer related content.
- Respondents from urban area make up 60% , suggesting that influencer marketing is more prevalent in these areas whereas the prevalence of influencer marketing in rural areas is low (21%).
- It was observed that 68% (102) of the respondents spend 1-5 hours daily which shows a high influencer content exposure.
- 55% (82) respondents agree that influencer recommendations effect their purchases.
- The study reveals that 31% (47) are satisfied whereas 18% (27)are not satisfied with their purchases indicating a potential issue in influencer trust or product quality.
- 19%(28) say that likes, shares and comments effect their shopping choices mostly or very much while 27%(41) say it doesn't affect them much.
- The figures show that 32% (51) of the respondents discuss occasionally or rarely about influencer content with family/ friends showing limited offline conversation.
- 100 respondents (67%) have never attended events organized by influencers suggesting only digital interaction.
- 42% (63) of the respondents engage “sometimes” with the influencer content while only 9% engage always.

4.2 ANALYSIS – II: FACTOR ANALYSIS

Factor Analysis: Factor analysis is a statistical method that groups observed variables into unobserved variables called factors in order to find underlying correlations between them.

This method simplifies complex data sets by lowering the quantity of variables, making it easier to interpret the data's structure.

The KMO and Bartlett's test measures were calculated to assess whether factor analysis was appropriate, and the results are shown in table 2.

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett's Test**KMO and Bartlett's Test**

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.812
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	602.249
	df	91
	Sig.	.000

To determine whether the variables in the sample are sufficient to correlate, the KMO measure of sampling adequacy was computed using the correlation test. In general, a satisfactory factor analysis cannot proceed unless the KMO value is greater than 0.5.

From table 2, it can be noticed that KMO value is 0.812. Evidence of a relation between the variables was also identified using the Bartlett's test of sphericity, which was significant at the 1% level.

Table 3: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.534	32.385	32.385	4.534	32.385	32.385	2.993	21.381	21.381
2	1.697	12.119	44.504	1.697	12.119	44.504	2.495	17.820	39.201
3	1.189	8.495	52.999	1.189	8.495	52.999	1.932	13.798	52.999
4	.985	7.037	60.036						
5	.864	6.169	66.205						
6	.832	5.944	72.148						
7	.719	5.139	77.287						
8	.609	4.348	81.635						
9	.590	4.216	85.852						

10	.471	3.366	89.218						
11	.446	3.187	92.405						
12	.421	3.005	95.411						
13	.362	2.587	97.998						
14	.280	2.002	100.000						

Statement	Component		
	1	2	3
Social media influencers significantly influence my purchasing decisions	.754	.141	.070
I often emulate the lifestyle choices of influencers I follow	.657	.039	.259
Influencers play crucial role in shaping trends and preferences	.116	.669	.257
I trust recommendations from influencers more than traditional advertising	.459	.310	.275
I believe influencers have a genuine impact on societal norms and values	.397	.473	.125
Social media interactions with influencers positively affect my social life	.523	.456	.150
I am aware of potential negative effects of influencer culture	-.072	.806	- .032
Influencers often promote unrealistic standards that may be harmful	.284	.560	- .418
I have changed my behaviour or preferences based on influenza recommendations	.541	.071	.438
The rise of influencers has altered the dynamics of traditional advertising	.056	.668	.357
I click links in influencers posts if the content interests me	.116	.264	.772
Influencers mentioning brands can influence my perception	.397	.113	.680
I follow hashtags of favourite influencers for relevant content	.660	.023	.334
I wish to become a social media influencer	.592	.039	- .120

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 4: Rotated Component Matrix^a

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.			
Rotation	Method:	Varimax	with Kaiser
Normalization.			
a. Rotation converged in 5 iterations.			

Total Variance explained: The eigenvalues, variance percentage, cumulative variance, and total variance of the variable chosen for the investigation are displayed in table 3.

According to the findings, 53% of the variance was explained by the first three components, each of whose eigenvalue was greater than one. We are able to minimize the number of components from 14 to three underlying factors, which is satisfactory.

The table 4 represents Rotated Component matrix. The variables emulating influencer lifestyle (0.657), following influencer hashtags (0.660), wanting to become an influencer (0.592) and behaviour change due to influencers (0.541) have high loadings on factor 1 representation. Thus the factor 1 can be named as Behavioural engagement. On factor 2, the variables influencer shape trends (0.669), influencers affect societal values (0.473), influencers promote unrealistic standards (0.560), awareness of negative effect (0.806) and influence on advertising (0.668) have high loadings. Thus factor 2 is named as perception of influence and societal role. On factor 3, the variables clicking links(0.772), Brand perception (0.680) and Behaviour change (0.438) have high loadings. Therefore, factor 3 is named as Brand interaction.

Then the factors, Behavioural Engagement, Perception of influence and societal role, Brand interaction had a high influence on the buying behaviour of consumers.

9. Conclusion:

The current study facilitates the understanding of multidimensional impact of social media influencers(SMIs) on consumer behaviour, preferably in the Indian context. As a result of the analysis carried out for 150 respondents across diverse demographics and geographics, several relevant conclusions were drawn associating with the stated objectives.

Primarily, the data reveals that influencer marketing is more prevalent in urban areas with majority of the respondents spending around 1-5 hours daily showing a high level of influencer content exposure.

Secondarily, it was observed that though the majority of the respondents engage only sometime with the influencer content, a significant percentage of them agree that influencer recommendations effect their purchases.

The factor analysis revealed 53% of the total variance is together explained by three distinct factors. Factor 1 captured items related to “Behavioural Engagement”, Factor 2 correspond to “Perception of influence and societal role” and Factor 3 represented “Brand Interaction”.

Each factor showed strong internal consistency and meaningful item loadings. Factor1 reflects active engagement with influencers, including behavioural mimicry and interaction. Factor 2 captures beliefs and awareness about the influence of social media influences on society and norms. Factor 3 is related to consumer interaction with brand related content through influencers.

These findings offer meaningful insight into how social media influencers affect user not only through marketing but also by shaping identity, behaviour and cultural awareness.

10. Scope for further research:

As the present study is more concentrated on few selected social media platforms like Youtube, Instagram, twitter etc leaving behind several other platforms like Reddit, telegram, Tiktok, Pinterest etc untouched. As there are many users of these platforms in the Indian market, it leaves the area open for further research. Besides these platforms, there is a scope to study the opinion of corporate and non corporate groups on social media influence.

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